

ized knapsack mistblower. We used a D-vac suction sampler to assess insect populations in 8 m² of each plot.

BPH populations in plots sprayed with methyl parathion and decamethrin were higher than in control plots. Plots

treated with monocrotophos yielded the most, followed by plots with al-phacypermethrin + BPMC (see table). Plots treated with cypermethrin and decamethrin yielded less than the control plots.

The results imply that methyl parathion and decamethrin could induce high BPH densities. Treated fields did not yield higher than the control, which suggests that insecticide applications might not benefit yields. □

Hourly catches of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB moth catches were recorded from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m. at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, for a 24-d period coinciding with peak brood emergence. Three traps—a local bamboo light trap with 40 W incandescent bulb, and modified Robinson light traps with 125 W mercury vapor lamp and 200 W incandescent bulb—were located 100 m apart. Moth catches were transferred to separate containers at hourly intervals, separated by sex, counted, and a cumulative percentage worked out (see figure).

Cumulative percentage of YSB catch in light traps at hourly intervals from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m.

Peak moth catch occurred at 9 to 10 p.m. Sixty-four percent of the females and 62% of the males were caught before

midnight. There was a slight spurt in moth activity from 1 to 4 a.m. for females and from 4 to 5 a.m. for males. □

Effect of rice stage and GLH density on pipunculid parasitism on green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* in Bali, Indonesia

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Pipunculid flies are natural enemies of GLH, a vector of rice tungro, but their activities in the tropics are not well known. Observations in major rice-producing areas of Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Bali, and Lombok from 1986 to 1990 showed cases in which pipunculid parasitism rate was more than 80%.

We surveyed 83 ricefields in asynchronously planted areas in Bali for this

Pipunculid parasitism on *N. virescens* in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season.^a

Rice crop age	Dry season			Wet season		
	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)
Nursery beds	63	6.3	43.6	84	7.1	62.0
3-4 WT	76	14.5	41.4	186	14.5	56.6
5-6 WT	151	10.6	21.1	738	21.8	16.0
7-8 WT	200	23.5	1.4	148	29.1	5.5
9-10 WT	-	-	-	203	26.1	8.6
Ratoon	105	6.7	47.8	64	28.1	14.3

^aWT = weeks after transplanting. MF = proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

study. GLH adults were collected by net sweeps in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season. Insects were dissected under a binocular microscope to observe for pipunculid larvae and for the proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

Relation of pipunculid parasitism rate to GLH adult density in ricefields 5-8 WT. Regression line is $Y = 17.5 + 10.5X$, $r = 0.49$ (<0.01), where Y is are sin-transformed.